

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE GEOGRAPHY TEACHING-LEARNING PROCESS IN 10th CLASS IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF SELES, ANGOLA

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Abstract: This article aims to identify the shortcomings observed in carrying out the methodological work of teaching Geography in the 10th grade in the Lyceum of the municipality of Seles, which weakens the direction of the teaching-learning process to fully prepare the individual for the demands of life individual and collective, as oriented in the Basic Law of the Education and Teaching System, in Angola. Grade 10 teachers and students have little participation in the development of geographic content, as it is an adaptation class. The quality of teaching and school performance are low, and the teaching methods and means used are not very adequate, due to the insufficient teaching methodological work that must be carried out with adequate teaching methods and means, through an active and participatory pedagogy. This weakness has a negative influence on the geography teaching-learning process, especially on the quality of teaching and school performance. The results were obtained through document review, interviews, surveys, and class observation, applied in the investigation to obtain the Master's degree in Education Sciences, option Teaching Geography, in the research line of the teaching-learning process of Geography, at the Higher Institute of Educational Sciences in Sumbe, in Angola.

Keywords: Education; Didactics of Geography; quality of teaching; school performance; teaching methodological work.

I. INTRODUCTION

The teaching-learning process of Geography in Grade 10 begins with the presentation of a physical map of the world that summarizes the physical aspects of the Earth. The themes that are developed are supported by photographs, maps, graphs, data tables, and boxes with information that allow the enrichment of knowledge. To motivate the interest of both students and teachers, a multitude of images are included in the text manual. [1] Although in the teaching-learning process of Geography of the 10th grade, there are the mentioned elements, observed insufficiencies in the accomplishment of the teaching methodological work that favors the direction of the process (guidance, execution and control of activities) to “prepare integral form the individual for the demands of individual and collective life” as stated in the Basic Law of the Education and Teaching System of Angola. [2] The results obtained during the investigation reflect the insufficiencies of the teachers in the development of the subjects of Geography of the 10th grade in Lyceum in Seles, in the municipality of Seles, province of Cuanza Sul, Angola. Grade 10 teachers and students have little participation in the development of geographic content, mainly because it is an adaptation class.

The quality of teaching and school performance is low, and the teaching methods and means used are not adequate. The identified results demonstrated that the teaching methodological work with adequate teaching methods and means through

an active and participatory pedagogy is weak, which negatively influences the teaching-learning process of Geography, especially in the quality of teaching and school performance.

II. STUDY METHODOLOGY

The research was carried out in the Lyceum of the municipality of Seles, with a population of 675 students from the 10th grade, of which 393 are male and 282 are female. 1 Director General and 1 Pedagogical Deputy Director of the Lyceum participated in the interview and 3 Geography teachers who teach in 10 classes, 7 in the Human Sciences course and 3 in Economics and Legal Sciences, participated in the survey. For this research, theoretical and empirical methods were used.

The research had an exploratory and explanatory approach in which information was collected on the teaching-learning process of Geography in the 10th grade at Lyceum in Seles and, in addition to recording and analyzing the phenomena studied, its causes were identified through the interpretation data, made possible by qualitative methods. Techniques of documentation, interviews, and questionnaires were used. [3, 4]

The methodology comprises the study of methods and the set of investigation procedures of the different sciences in terms of their foundations and validity, distinguishing itself from the techniques that are the application of methods. The techniques and resources or teaching means complement the methodology, made available to the teacher to enrich the teaching-learning process. [5]

The documentation was used to identify, in the Basic Law of the Education and Teaching System of Angola [2], the definition of Education, its purpose and the general and specific objectives of education and teaching in the second cycle of secondary education. The legal regime for the initial training of kindergarten teachers, primary school teachers and secondary school teachers in Angola [6] made it possible to identify the social demand for teacher training and the corresponding guidelines for the development of professional skills.

The 10th-grade Geography teaching program, in the second cycle of secondary education, prepared by the National Institute of Research and Development of Education (INIDE), was used to identify the themes of the contents taught and the insufficiencies presented by teachers and students in their development. In addition, the text manual and other teaching means such as the maps that are used in the teaching-learning process of Geography in Angola were consulted. The information taken from these sources was recorded and used during the development of the research.

The general director and the pedagogical director of the high school in Seles were given structured interviews, the questions were previously established and directed with a certain internal articulation to obtain easily categorizable answers, getting closer to the questionnaire, although without its impersonality.

The survey by a questionnaire applied to the teachers contained questions systematically articulated to obtain written information in order to know the opinion of the teachers on the characteristics of the teaching-learning process of Geography of the 10th grade in Lyceum in Seles. The clearly formulated questions were objective and relevant to the object of study so that they were well understood by the teachers and elicited objective answers, avoiding doubts, ambiguities, and laconic answers. In some cases, open questions were presented that allowed further explanation of the object of study.

In observing the phenomena, participant research was used, sharing the experience of the researched subjects and participating in a systematic and permanent way, throughout the time of the research, and its activities. The researcher interacted with the teachers and students following all the situations of the actions practiced in the classroom, observing their manifestations and the situations that occurred in the classroom while descriptively recording all the observed elements as well as the analyses and considerations made during that observation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Education is a broad concept that refers to the process of unilateral development of the personality, involving the formation of human qualities – physical, moral, intellectual, aesthetic – with a view to guiding human activity in its relationship with the social environment, in a given context. context of social relations. [5]

In Angola, the Basic Law of the Education and Teaching System – Law nº 17/16, of October 7 – in article 2, point 1, states: “Education is a planned and systematized process of teaching and learning that aims to prepare integrates the individual to the demands of individual and collective life”. [2]

In point 2 of article 2 of the aforementioned Law, it reads: ... “The individual develops in human coexistence in order to be able to face the main challenges of society, (...), of the environment, as well as in the process of scientific, technical, technological, economic, social and cultural development of the country”. [2]

The general objectives of Education, in Angola, are expressed in Chapter I, Article 4, of the Basic Law of the Education and Teaching System, – Law nº 17/16 of October 7th – and the specific objectives of the II Cycle of Secondary Education General are declared in Chapter III, article 33 of the same Law.

According to the National Institute for Research and Development of Education (INIDE) the specific objectives of the subject of Geography in the II Cycle of General Secondary Education are established in terms of knowledge, skills, attitudes and values and it is oriented that the teaching-learning must be based on an active and participatory pedagogy, centered on teacher-student interaction and on a dynamic relationship with knowledge. [7]

The demands that the development of society imposes on the educational process do not only refer to the volume of knowledge, the system of skills attitudes and values that the student has to master, develop and demonstrate during certain stages. They impose a full integration of the individual in the society in which he lives, who is qualified, both personally and professionally, to assume responsible and conscious behavior in decision-making. [7]

The inclusion of Geography in the areas of Human Sciences and Economic and Legal Sciences, in their specific training components, had as guiding principles the understanding of general aspects of planetology, taking into account that the planet is not isolated in the Universe; the understanding of general characteristics typical of other regions of the planet as a logical sequence of the approaches carried out in the I Cycle of General Secondary Education; the understanding of relationships between human beings and their environment; the understanding of issues related to the production and distribution of resources and development. [7]

The principles that determine the teaching of Geography in General Secondary Education in Angola are the following: the scientific, objective and systemic nature of teaching; the formative character of the subject (development of positive attitudes and values); encouraging students to carry out learning situations; the interaction of theoretical content with practice; direct sensory perception (experiences, observations of reality); the concreteness in the explanation of the content. [7] As can be seen in the development of the geography teaching-learning process, the application of multiple methodologies and strategies that are likely to create opportunities for individual and collective awareness is required. In the approach of geographic contents, it is necessary [7]

“Start whenever possible from concrete situations and direct observation of reality and/or images, establishing analogies with the student's personal experience; placing students in problematic situations that encourage their initiative and contribute to the development of their critical sense and decision-making capacity; promote teamwork as a way to develop cooperation, mutual aid, and socialization; use a variety of methodological resources such as observation and exploration of images, the narration of facts and experiences, individualized reading of texts, discussion/debate of community situations, etc., in order to diversify learning; use the local environment (village, commune, municipality) as an essential didactic resource, bearing in mind that learning must have meaning for the student's interest and experience; articulate the specific content of the discipline with other disciplines in the pedagogical performance”.

In this sense [8], “reflection on what Geography is, in fact, and updated knowledge are the first condition for the teacher and the student to be able to deal with the Geography Teaching Methodology” that:

“(…) deals with the teaching-learning of contents and methods and the assessment of the respective learning, so it necessarily has to deal with the knowledge that the discipline in question deals with; the way of translating, adapting, unfolding, adapting them, bearing in mind the students for whom the course is intended; how this knowledge was constructed by the scientific community; and the processes of construction of knowledge by students, in class, guided by a teacher”.

In reality, the “translation”, the adaptation, and the adequacy of scientific knowledge so that students can build their knowledge are extremely important in the geography teaching-learning process. To this end, teaching methodological work is needed, which manifests itself, fundamentally, “in the development with quality of the teaching-learning process, to achieve an adequate integration of research and work activity with tasks of high social impact and other tasks of extracurricular activities carried out by students”. [9] The analysis of the teaching methodological work in the teaching of

Geography serves to reveal whether the activities developed by the teacher are allowing the realization of practices that integrate the teaching-learning process.

The Dictionary of the Contemporary Portuguese Language of the Academy of Sciences of Lisbon presents, among others, the following definitions [10]: a) methodology – study of methods applied in different sciences according to the laws of reasoning; b) methodologist – professor who guides internships in the professionalization process; c) methodological – related to conducting a knowledge acquisition process. This conception fits the teaching methodological work that, in the present research, is understood as being the work that the teacher carries out in the didactic scope for the improvement of the activities relative to the conduction of the teaching-learning process of Geography.

There are different ways that characterize the development of the teaching methodological work, from the individual work of the teacher in his scientific, technical, and pedagogical self-preparation with a view to carrying out the teaching-learning process to the work in groups, in methodological meetings, to analyze the outline of the process, its execution and result, through its control. When preparing the subject, one should consider the level of development reached by the teachers in the different aspects of the methodological work, which is understood as “the administrative dimension (of management) of the teaching-learning process, through which both planning and organization are developed. as its regulation and control. [11] The same author clarifies [12]:

“The planning of the teaching-learning process corresponds to the determination of objectives and contents; the organization with the possible forms, means and methods to be used; the regulation (management) the operative adequacy of the process; the control with the determination of the degree in which, in the development, the process approaches the objective, the student's learning and formation and its rectification”.

The teacher's methodological work is essential for optimizing the teaching-learning process, as it enables the exchange of experiences among teachers and stimulates a spirit of competence among them, without interfering with the freedom that each teacher has during the development of their class. This freedom is not infinite, it takes place within certain limits: in the objectives and contents of the subject which, in turn, forms part of a larger system of subjects, the curricular program of the class in which one works. In this context, the teacher has the right and the duty to manifest his creativity and stimulate the creativity of his students. [5]

To approach aspects of content and methodology of the programs of the different disciplines, with the purpose of raising the theoretical, practical, and methodological level of the professors, methodological meetings are used, also called methodological classes. These serve for the analysis of the experiences obtained, as well as the control of the results of the teaching-learning process, in the same way, they can be used for the half-yearly and annual methodological balance, according to what had been planned. In the methodological meeting, elaborated questions can be presented on the foreseen theme around which adjustments will be debated and adopted. [12]

The main subjects that can be approached in the methodological meeting are diagnosis and direction of the teaching-learning process; students' learning difficulties in one or more subjects; effectiveness of the methodological work carried out; effectiveness of educational teaching work and its results; improvement of educational teaching work during the teaching of subjects, planning, development and control of students' independent work; more effective methods in educational teaching work; improvement of teaching methods; planning and organization of learning assessment; analysis of the evaluation results of a class, quarter, semester or academic year; the result of visits and other forms of control used. [12] In this way, teachers deepen their knowledge of the steps leading to the geography teaching-learning process.

The methodological classes are a form of methodological work by the teacher whose function is to guide the teachers about the methods, procedures and means of teaching that must be used in the teaching-learning process of the students, in the development of the main forms of organization of teaching, of themes and disciplines.

The guiding character of the methodological classes manifests itself in two ways: the demonstrative methodological class, which takes place in the classroom context, in the presence of students and other teachers, and the instructive methodological class, which requires a collective and profound analysis of the discipline's program, of the lesson plan, according to the objective and the selected methodological problem. [12, 13, 14]

The essence of the methodological classes is the application of knowledge through concrete exercises and the development of a system of theoretical and practical skills and habits related to the sphere of professional action; favor the performance of tasks of a professional nature; they demand mastery of content and practical work from the professor, as well as skills to

determine the appropriate sequence of exercises and tasks, with pedagogical expertise, to grade the requirements placed on students. [13, 14] Methodological work is necessary for the efficient development of the geography teaching-learning process.

During the interview, the Director and Pedagogical Deputy Director of the Lyceum in the municipality of Seles declared that the institution has 13 classes in the 10th grade, 3 of which are in Physical and Biological Sciences, 7 in the Human Sciences course and 3 in Economic and Legal Sciences; the 10 classes in which Geography is taught have 675 students, of which 393 are male and 282 are female. Among the main causes of failure in the 2019 academic year, the Director mentioned the students' lack of interest in the subject of Geography because it seems to be a purely theoretical subject.

In Lyceum, teachers have held methodological meetings to overcome the difficulties that arise in the teaching-learning process of geography; however, the results of these meetings are insufficient to improve the quality of teaching and school performance. The methodological meetings, as designated by the directors, do not meet the required scientific and technical requirements, and therefore did not significantly contribute to the improvement of the teaching methodological work.

The Pedagogical Director and Deputy Director of the Lyceum declared that they had already attended some Geography classes and considered it necessary to hold methodological meetings for the training of teachers because knowledge must be renewed over time, according to the dynamics of science and the local context.

Teachers A and B, male, with a degree in Educational Sciences, in the geography teaching option, considered the geography teaching-learning process carried out at Lyceum do Seles to be good. Among the main difficulties they face at the institution, they mentioned the lack of Geography maps, text manuals and geographical atlases. Also, they highlighted that students have difficulties in perceiving the geographical phenomena of the Universe as well as the origin of the components of the same system; difficulties in perceiving the representation of the Earth, the calculations and the reduction of distances from reality on paper.

Teachers declared that they have addressed the issue of protecting the environment and considered it important to practice integral field work with students; considered that support material and the use of methods appropriately for each topic are necessary so that they contribute to improving the quality of teaching and school performance.

Teacher C, a female, with a degree in Educational Sciences, in the geography teaching option, considered the Geography teaching process that takes place at the Seles Lyceum to be good. He has addressed the issue of environmental protection and considers it important to practice integral fieldwork with students. Considered it necessary to educate students in the culture of scientific research in order to develop levels of knowledge outside the classroom; he also considered important the implementation of scientific journeys and full field practice classes with students from the same class or more classes.

In general, the 3 professors mentioned the following aspects as the main difficulties in developing the themes:

Theme I – The Earth: global environment. The Universe: Its Formation. In this subject, the teachers considered that the lack of teaching hinders the understanding of knowledge about the solar system and the Earth-Moon system, as well as its movements and consequences.

Theme II – Geographic representations. In this sense, the difficulty lies in the lack of teaching means, precisely geographical atlases and maps, to show the types of cartographic projections and the terrestrial globe. On the other hand, the problem lies in solving the mathematical calculations related to distances on the ground and converting them to scale on paper.

Theme III – Our atmosphere: Problems and possible solutions. The difficulty lies in identifying the values of high or low pressure and their application in the determination of baric or barometric centers, taking into account the equivalence between the measurement in millimeters of mercury (mm/Hg) or in millibars (mb).

The 3 teachers also mentioned that students have difficulties in understanding the geographic phenomena of the Universe, as well as the origin of the other components of the same system, have difficulties in understanding the different forms of representation of the Earth (cartographic projections) and difficulties in interpreting the different geographic phenomena represented in the different maps.

In order to improve the geography teaching-learning process, the teachers made the following proposals: holding methodological meetings to exchange experiences between teachers from different schools; carrying out an integral field

practice for the observation and identification of the components of the geographic space in the locality; acquisition of teaching resources, such as manuals, maps, terrestrial globe, and geographic atlas of Secondary Education.

The class observed at Lyceum in Seles, on November 25, 2020, had the general objective of observing the teacher's procedures during the class to assess the efficiency of the teaching-learning process of Geography in the 10th grade, in the Human Sciences course. As for the positive aspects of the class, the teacher wrote the summary with the recommended details (place, date and class), clearly expressed the purpose of the class, controlled the students' attendance and reviewed the main aspects of the previous class. The class observed is part of Theme 1- The Earth: Global Environment. Subtheme - Earth surface movements: plate tectonics.

During the class, the teacher used the world map, demonstrated a good command of the content, led the students to active participation. Due to the lack of 10th grade Geography manuals, he dictated the notes and in the absence of a geographic atlas for secondary education, he used the geographic atlas of Angola: volume 2. In consolidating knowledge, he summarized the class and answered the concerns presented by the students through the questions to clarify doubts. At the end of the class, he guided the homework in order to consolidate the learning of the theory of plate tectonics. Class time was properly controlled.

As for the negative aspects of the class, the teacher did not put the closing line of the summary to express that the other part of the board would be used for the development of the class; he did not use the pointer to limit the different tectonic plates being studied on the world map; he did not use the eraser, he used his hand when he needed to erase some words on the board; due to the lack of 10th-grade geography manuals, he dictated the subject and made use of the geographic atlas volume 2 when he should have used the geographic atlas of secondary education, as it was the most up-to-date.

IV. CONCLUSION

The theoretical and methodological foundations, and legal documents consulted on the teaching methodological work in the teaching and learning process of Geography contribute to the promotion of active and participative pedagogy of students. However, the teachers of the Lyceum do Seles do not adequately take advantage of this knowledge to deepen and consolidate the contents of the respective process.

The analysis of the teaching methodological work in the teaching-learning process of Grade 10 Geography through interviews with the principals, surveys by questionnaire to the teachers, observation of the class, and review of legal and methodological documents allowed identifying the shortcomings that weaken the respective process. Grade 10 teachers and students show poor participation and weaknesses in geographic content, mainly because it is an adaptation class. The quality of teaching and school performance is low, and the teaching methods and means used are not adequate.

The insufficiency of teachers in finding methods to enhance the learning of the content makes the students less oriented in learning. The identified results demonstrated that the methodological work of the teacher through an active and participatory pedagogy, based on the appropriate teaching methods and means, influences the quality of teaching and school performance.

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